

Appendix B – Personality Test

Section 01: Demographic Information

1) How old are you?

2) How would you describe your gender?

(Male/ Female/ Prefer to self-describe as:/ Prefer not to answer)

3) Country of your residence?

4) What is your highest educational qualification?

5) How many years have you been in the software industry?

6) Is eliciting/ analysing. prioritising/ modelling/ managing software requirements a part of your job? (Yes/ No)

7) How often do you elicit/ analyse/ prioritize/ manage software requirements as a part of your job?

(Almost every day/ Couple of times a week/ Couple of times a month/ Couple of times a year (or very rarely))

8) What is your current job title/ job role?

9) Your current job responsibilities include: (please rate the following based on your involvement): close-ended question with the Likert scale

from “Never” to “Always”.

- Collaborate with the stakeholders to elicit requirements
- Documenting software requirements specifications according to standard templates
- Lead requirements analysis and verification
- Participate in requirements prioritisation
- Manage requirements throughout the project

10) Is there are any other job responsibilities that you involve in apart from the above list, please mention:

Section 02: Personality Assessment

1) This section contains phrases describing people’s behaviours. Please go through the instructions listed above before you rate the phrases. Please indicate to what extent each of the following statements applies to you.

(Rate with the Likert scale from “very inaccurate” to “very accurate”)

- list of 120 statements can be found in the following table.

1. I worry about things	61. I am afraid of many things
2. I make friends easily	62. I avoid contact with others
3. I have a vivid imagination	63. I love to daydream
4. I trust others	64. I trust what people say
5. I complete tasks successfully	65. I handle tasks smoothly
6. I get angry easily	66. I lose my temper
7. I love large parties	67. I prefer to be alone
8. I believe in the importance of art	68. I do not like poetry
9. I use others for my own ends	69. I take advantage of others
10. I like to tidy up	70. I leave a mess in my room
11. I often feel blue	71. I am often down in the dumps
12. I take charge	72. I take control of things
13. I experience my emotions intensely	73. I rarely notice my emotional reactions
14. I love to help others	74. I am indifferent to the feeling of others
15. I keep my promises	75. I break rules
16. I find it difficult to approach others	76. I only feel comfortable with friends
17. I am always busy	77. I do a lot in my spare time
18. I prefer a variety of routine	78. I dislike changes
19. I love a good fight	79. I insult people
20. I work hard	80. I do just enough work to get by
21. I go on binges	81. I easily resist temptations
22. I love excitement	82. I enjoy being reckless
23. I love to read challenging materials	83. I have difficulty understanding abstract ideas
24. I believe that I am better than others	84. I have a high opinion of myself
25. I am always prepared	85. I waste my time
26. I panic easily	86. I feel that I'm unable to deal with things
27. I radiate joy	87. I love life
28. I tend to vote for liberal political candidates	88. I tend to vote for conservative political candidates
29. I sympathise with the homeless	89. I am not interested in other people's problems
30. I jump into things without thinking	90. I rush into things
31. I fear for the worst	91. I get stressed out easily
32. I feel comfortable around people	92. I keep others at a distance
33. I enjoy wild flights of fantasy	93. I like to get lost in thought
34. I believe that others have good intentions	94. I distrust people
35. I excel in what I do	95. I know how to get things done
36. I get irritated easily	96. I am not easily annoyed
37. I talk to a lot of different people at parties	97. I avoid crowds
38. I see beauty in the things that others might not notice	98. I do not enjoy going to art museums
39. I cheat to get ahead	99. I obstruct others' plans
40. I often forgot to put things back in their proper place	100. I leave my belongings around

41. I dislike myself	101. I feel comfortable with myself
42. I try to lead others	102. I wait for others to lead the way
43. I feel others' emotions	103. I don't understand people who get emotional
44. I am concerned about others	104. I take no time for others
45. I tell the truth	105. I break my promises
46. I am afraid to draw attention to myself	106. I am not bothered by difficult social situations
47. I am always on the go	107. I like to take it easy
48. I prefer to stick with the things I know	108. I am attracted to conventional ways
49. I yell at people	109. I get back at others
50. I do more than what's expected of me	110. I put little time and effort into my work
51. I rarely overindulge	111. I am able to control my cravings
52. I seek adventure	112. I act wild and crazy
53. I avoid philosophical discussions	113. I am not interested in theoretical discussions
54. I think highly of myself	114. I boast about my virtues
55. I carry out my plans	115. I have difficulty starting tasks
56. I become overwhelmed by events	116. I remain calm under pressure
57. I have a lot of fun	117. I look at the bright side of life
58. I believe that there is no absolute right or wrong	118. I believe that we should be tough on crime
59. I feel sympathy for those who are worse off than myself	119. I try not to think about the needy
60. I make rash decisions	120. I act without thinking

2) Do you wish to receive your individual personality profile? (Yes/No)

3) If yes, please enter your name and email address